

**CDB / CARICOM / OECS Model
Learning Recovery and Enhancement
Programme for Caribbean Schools**

Let's REAP!

Roadmap for Principals

<https://lreap.info>

**Organisation of
Eastern Caribbean States**

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All **Let's REAP!** materials are available from all partner organisations: www.caribank.org/lreap, caricom.org/lreap and oecs.int/lreap, as well as at lreap.info.

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Abbreviations and acronyms

AfL	Assessment for Learning
CARICOM	Caribbean Community
CDB	Caribbean Development Bank
COVID-19	Coronavirus disease 2019 caused by SARS-CoV-2
EdTech	Educational technology
ICT	Information and communication technologies
Let's REAP!	Learning Recovery and Enhancement Programme (L-R-EA-P)
MoE	Ministry of Education
OECS	Organization of Eastern Caribbean States
OER	Open Educational Resources
PD	Professional development
SEMH	Social emotional and mental health
SPED	Special education and disability
TPD	Teacher professional development

1. Introduction to Let's REAP!

The COVID-19 pandemic brought significant disruption to the education systems of the Member States of the CARICOM, CDB and the OECS and other parts of the region, exacerbating existing stresses. Moreover, the pandemic further widened the education gaps between high-performing and low-performing students, particularly for already disadvantaged learners. Disadvantaged learners include learners of low socio-economic status and those that have special educational needs or a disability (SPED). When the pandemic hit, there were many impacts caused by uncertainties on teachers, on students, on families, and so forth. Now, it is clear that the COVID-19 pandemic has brought significant disruption to the education systems of all countries around the world. In the Caribbean, this has exacerbated the effects of existing stresses and widening education gaps between high-performing and low-performing students, particularly for already disadvantaged learners (such as those with disabilities or from low-income families).

To address the learning needs brought about by COVID-19, the CDB, CARICOM and OECS commissioned a Learning Recovery and Enhancement Programme, abbreviated as L-R-EA-P and pronounced

Let's REAP!

The focus of **Let's REAP!** is to promote learning improvement and recovery for those students struggling as a result of COVID-19 disruptions. However, the programme also intends to address longer-standing issues that the pandemic has exacerbated and to build the resilience of national education systems to the occurrence of other natural hazards (such as flooding, hurricanes, and volcanic activity) prevalent in the region. **Let's REAP!**, for education in the Caribbean, seeks to

Recover, Improve, Transform

For **Let's REAP!** to be effective, a multi-pronged approach must be taken, supporting national ministries, principals, and teachers; such a broad approach will set in motion processes that ultimately support learners to improve learning outcomes. That is to say: **Let's REAP!** is an intervention for children and young persons, but it is also an intervention for the system around the child: Teachers, principals, parents, community and government.

1. Introduction to Let's REAP!

Figure 1. The roadmap for principals. This graphic is also available as a poster.

The components and action items for principals shown in [Figure 1. The roadmap for principals](#), in plain text, are as follows:

1. Leadership & accountability
 - Establish Communities of Practice among principals
 - Ensure that structures are in place to allow teachers to conduct monitoring and reporting on student learning
2. School management & communication
 - Establish and manage LRIP Team
 - Coordinate teacher CPD
 - Coordinate data collection and planning for learning
3. Regional & national partnerships
 - Share information about regional and national progress with teachers
4. Teacher support & collaboration
 - Establish school-based Community of Practice
 - Implement differentiated instruction programme
5. Formative assessment
 - Diagnostic tests developed and administered
 - Implement formative/continuous assessment
 - Support teachers in the development of individualised learning plans and assessments
6. Inclusion, SPED, wellbeing
 - Develop inclusive learning environment
 - Coordinate psycho-social wellbeing programmes for students and teachers
 - Manage referrals & support

7. Resources & curriculum

- Facilitate the introduction of new curriculum material
- Encourage teachers to source and use relevant learning resources
- Encourage and monitor curriculum innovation among teachers

8. Engagement with parents & family

- Coordinate the provision of psycho-social support for parents
- Strengthen and encourage dis-engaged parents to support student learning
- Report to PTA on LRIP progress

9. Engagement with community & community organisations

- Engage local organisations to work with vulnerable learners
- Mobilise support for LRIP from community leaders.

The implementation of **Let's REAP!** will be driven by principals across OECS and CARICOM. Therefore, this document gives specific guidance on how to successfully execute the recovery programme. This document is primarily aimed at principals, but it is also relevant for other school staff.

There are several important considerations (further detailed in Section [4.4. Important considerations](#)):

- **Let's REAP!** is context-specific. The programme can be modified to suit each school's specific context.
- **Let's REAP!** is not only focused on immediate recovery. It focuses on improvement and ultimately has a transformational goal.
- **Let's REAP!** is for all schools and all grades. In other words, it supports all students.
- Management, monitoring and communication are the keys to success for **Let's REAP!**
- Principals should ensure that all teachers participate in **Let's REAP!** Where possible, the unions should be engaged too.
- **Let's REAP!** places the school at the centre of focus. The school is the unit of transformation.

1. Introduction to Let's REAP!

- In **Let's REAP!**, the school is the sphere of control of the principal, who is acting autonomously and in an empowered way. If necessary, the programme can be implemented without external help.

Further details are available ([↑Let's REAP! — Overview](#)). There are also accompanying documents for Ministries ([↑Let's REAP! — A Roadmap for Ministries](#)) as well as regional organisations ([↑Let's REAP! — A Roadmap for IGOs](#)). A unique feature of **Let's REAP!** is the coordination across different locations and different areas. The figures in [↑Let's REAP! — Overview](#) illustrate how the programme's components interlock and combine. This roadmap graphic is also available as a [↑Poster](#).

2. The role of principals and schools

In this section, we turn to the specific actions for principals relating to the nine components. In brief, the nine components, as shown in [Figure 1 \(Roadmap for principals\)](#), are:

1. Leadership and accountability;
2. School management and communication;
3. Regional and national partnerships;
4. Teacher support and collaboration;
5. Formative assessment;
6. Inclusion, SPED, wellbeing;
7. Resources and curriculum;
8. Engagement with parents and family;
9. Engagement with community and community organisations.

A navigable menu to all the components can be found in the [Guide to this document](#) (below).

[Figure 2](#) shows the different actions for principals and other school staff relating to the nine components of **Let's REAP!**.

Figure 2. This figure shows the nine components of Let's REAP! relating to principals, teachers, and students.

The diagram shows the nine components (labelled 1–9). It shows 'School 1' (your school), with the principal (P), the vice-principal (VP) and some teachers (T). Some students are also represented (S). The two Communities of Practice (CoPs) through which the principals will implement the programme are indicated (COP 1, COP 2). COP 1 is the community of practice centred on the school, instigated through Component 2, which implements various components (4, 5, 6, but also 8 and 9). COP 2 is the Community of Practice of the principals, instigated through Component 1.

Guide to this document

Click on this symbol in the header of the document to jump back to this guide.

Click any section title below to jump to the section.

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2	3.2. School management and communication (C2L3)	5.2. School management and communication
3	3.3. Regional and national partnerships (C3L3)	5.3. Regional and national partnerships
4	3.4. Teacher support and collaboration (C4L3)	5.4. Teacher support & collaboration
5	3.5. Formative assessment (C5L3)	5.5. Formative assessment
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7	3.7. Resources and curriculum (C7L3)	5.7. Resources and curriculum
8	3.8. Engagement with parents and families (C8L3)	5.8. Engagement with parents and families
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Guide to implementation			
4. Step-by-step implementation			
4.1. Form a local/district group of principals and vice-principals	4.2. Constitute a Let's REAP! implementation team in your school	4.3. Start implementing	4.4. Important considerations

3. Overview of the nine components

We now turn to the nine components and briefly summarise them. The components are described from the principals' perspective. Where relevant, we touch on how components are implemented in other locations.

In this section, we use the Component/Location abbreviations, where 'C' denotes the component and 'L' the location, with L3 being the school: principals, teachers, children and young people, as well as those around the school: parents and the community.

Remember that you can use the icon at the top right of each page to jump back to the document overview.

3.1. Leadership and accountability (C1L3)

Leadership and accountability are essential themes and form Component 1 of **Let's REAP!**. As described further below, in this component, principals and vice-principals form a community of practice (CoP) with other principals and vice-principals. This community of practice is a small group of 6–10 principals and vice-principals (across 3–5 schools). This community of practice focuses on school leadership for learning recovery.

At the very least, this CoP is supported by a rich set of materials, which groups of principals/vice-principals can draw on to support their work in the CoP. The Leadership programme is designed to cover urgent matters (such as the teacher professional development implementation for recovery, see below) and aspects to improve leadership (based on the Leadership for Learning approach).

The principals/vice-principals are the primary agents of transformation. Using approaches known as 'circle of friends', 'learning circles' or 'teacher group meetings', principals/vice-principals have the agency to make far-reaching changes in their schools. This approach essentially enables peer-mentoring processes, making 'leadership' part of a sustainable culture of transformation.

The respective Ministry of Education in participating states will support the leadership programme (C1L2). For example, the Ministry might provide additional materials, additional guidance, perhaps a hotline or coaching support. However, this will not involve direct training of principals. We need to build a programme that can reach all principals, all teachers and all schools. The past has shown that this is hard to achieve effectively through traditional top-down training. In this approach, the agency remains with the principals/vice-principals.

3.2. School management and communication (C2L3)

The programme for principals (part of Component 1) focuses not only on developing leadership and accountability, but also on the implication of this for school management and improving communication within the school and beyond the school. Under Component 2, **school management and communication**, principals work with the school management team. It may be necessary to set up such a team if it does not yet exist. We will refer to this team as the school-based **Let's REAP!** team.

The **Let's REAP!** team has a number of important functions. The most important function is to orchestrate the implementation of the remaining components, particularly Components 4–9. This includes managing student allocation to specific learning recovery activities, teacher professional development and collecting / utilising school data. The **Let's REAP!** team will also relay school data to the relevant government departments, for both national monitoring (C2L2) and regional monitoring (C2L1).

3.3. Regional and national partnerships (C3L3)

For Component 3 on **regional and national partnerships**, principals do not have any specific actions, as this work primarily takes place within the national ministries (C3L2), between states and among regional organisations (C3L1).

3.4. Teacher support and collaboration (C4L3)

One of the most critical aspects of the programme is to form a **school-based community of practice** that consists of all teachers at your school and other school-based staff (whether they are at the school or working from home). This community of practice is school-based because the group of teachers at any one school are collectively responsible for student learning at that school. This collective responsibility for a particular group of students is particularly important.

The school-based community of practice will undertake school-based teacher professional development (TPD). Such school-based TPD might be quite different from other training that teachers may have attended. The TPD takes place in hourly weekly meetings that focus on improving student learning. We may say that the sole purpose of this community of practice is to improve student learning, i.e., bring about learning recovery and improvement. There are many other things that may be needed in specific schools, but they only become relevant to this community of practice to the degree that they focus on learning recovery and improvement.

Such topics, of course, include improvement of subject pedagogy. Improvement of subject pedagogy means utilising diagnostic testing to devise student learning plans (Component 5), creating truly inclusive learning environments (Component 6) and utilising state-of-the-art learning resources (Component 7), as well as including parents and the community as learning partners (Component 8 and Component 9). In this way, Component 4 on teacher support and collaboration provides a red thread through the remaining components.

This community of practice needs leaders who ensure that the component is successful. The community will be facilitated by the school-based **Let's REAP!** team, which in turn is managed by you, the principal. Materials to support your work, and the TPD in particular, are available. We note that the materials used for TPD materials are tailored to the local contexts for each context by each ministry of education (C4L2). The materials are based on model materials developed regionally (C4L1).

Another important step in this component is to put in place measures to implement differentiated instruction to promote inclusion, particularly for the most vulnerable students. To accomplish this, work closely with teams and other school leaders.

3.5. Formative Assessment (C5L3)

Let's REAP! allocates Component 5 to **formative assessment, including diagnostic testing and the development of student learning plans**. This is a pivotal component because it provides feedback loops between the planning of recovery and improvement activities and actual student learning.

The administration of tests is planned through the teacher professional development meetings (Component 4). Ultimately, the **Let's REAP!** team and principal need to ensure that *all* students are tested. However, the testing alone is not sufficient: The test results must be considered for each child and appropriate learning plans must be devised and implemented. Outcomes of the tests and progress with learning plans are communicated to the relevant ministries. At national level, the results are further analysed (C5L2) and passed to regional agencies (C5L1).

We note that formative/diagnostic assessments can be undertaken in a range of ways. For more formal diagnostic tests, e.g., using ASER¹ or ICAN,² the test is administered directly by the teachers or done with paper and pencil. Tests could also be administered digitally. However, formative assessment goes far beyond written tests, and includes approaches such as continuous assessment (e.g., student demonstrations), methods used for individual or group work (e.g., traffic lights) and so forth.

Support teachers in planning and administering formative assessments regularly. Ensure that formative assessment data is included in learning outcomes and data analysis.

¹ <http://www.asercentre.org/>

² International Common Assessment of Numeracy

<https://palnetwork.org/introducing-ican-international-common-assessment-of-numeracy-as-a-global-learning-metric/>

3.6. Inclusion, SPED, wellbeing (C6L3)

Component 7 focuses on **inclusive practices, SPED and wellbeing** (socio-emotional and mental health). Important steps need to be taken to make learning environments in the Caribbean more inclusive, allowing each learner to succeed. For this, radical steps must be taken. This does include provision for specialist training, specialist teachers and educational psychologists / school counsellors (C6L2). The **Let's REAP!** team must implement the proper referral protocols in place to identify and address learning needs of all students, including those with special needs. Where available, schools need to collaborate with SPED specialists and relevant national and international disability organisations to advocate, share information and best practice, access resources and so on in an effort to strengthen the SPED department. However, there is also significant work to be done in changing attitudes towards inclusive education. **Let's REAP!** contributes to this through advocacy at the school level, among parents and the community.

Further, we have to recognise the importance of mental health and mental wellbeing. The pandemic as well as some of the previous challenges have posed severe challenges, not just for students, but for everybody including teachers, principals and parents. As part of this component, we explore options for mental health and wellbeing.

3.7. Resources and curriculum (C7L3)

Over time, **Let's REAP!** will introduce new **resources and new curriculum elements** that are developed at national (C7L2) and regional level (C7L1). The introduction of such new elements will take place through the teacher professional development sessions (C4L3). Therefore, while these resources are being developed, it is important that principals and the **Let's REAP!** team makes the teacher professional development sessions as successful as possible; this will make the school and teachers as prepared as possible for new resources to arrive.

Part of **resources and new curriculum elements** involve encouraging curriculum innovation among teachers and resource sourcing to promote the use of high-quality material for teaching and learning.

3.8. Engagement with parents and families (C8L3)

The pandemic and other disasters are stressful times for parents, families and caregivers. Parents are just facing issues regarding mental health, job security, looking after the family, but also have to undertake homeschooling and are naturally concerned about the progress of their children. During the pandemic, many schools and education departments produced content to guide **parents, families and caregivers** in assisting their children at home. Such content will be reviewed and incorporated in the **Let's REAP!** by national ministries (C8L2) and regionally (C8L1).

Based on the materials provided, schools can take action in their work with parents. Teachers can apply protocols for engaging with parents and find alternative ways to reach parents who are reluctant to engage. Schools can strengthen links with both local and national parent-teacher associations, as they are important partners in building relationships with parents. These processes are initiated by the **Let's REAP!** team at each school, ultimately overseen by the principal.

In addition, the guide makes provision for **psychosocial support** for parents. As noted above, the home has become an integral part of learning during the pandemic, which has meant added responsibilities for parents. Promoting the wellbeing of parents will equip them to function more effectively in supporting learning at home. Likewise, it is important to find ways to strengthen and encourage **disengaged parents** to ensure that students who are most in need of support are attended to.

3.9. Engagement with community and community organisations (C9L3)

Community and community organisations can play an important role. They offer much needed support for children and young people, as well as for parents, families and caregivers. Community is important to the success of **Let's REAP!**, not least because schools already have partnerships with local community clubs, professionals and so on. Therefore, schools should review existing partnerships and seek potential new ones, particularly partnerships that can benefit vulnerable children. This should be accomplished in collaboration with staff, supported by strong monitoring and evaluations frameworks. Principals and the **Let's REAP!** team must ensure that community relations are established and maintained. This includes a focus on shared goals/values between school and community partners. Schools may also want to offer support to community organisations, ensuring they are empowered to contribute to **Let's REAP!**.

We note that, from a schools' perspective, the nine **Let's REAP!** components are implemented through two communities of practice. The two communities of practice focus on student learning — learning recovery and improvement. However, in **Let's REAP!**, there are other communities of practice, such as a community of practice of implementers at the ministry. Similarly, there may well be possibilities for community organisations to collaborate and form groups of practice around the **Let's REAP!** implementation. Teachers who have experience with the school-based **Let's REAP!** implementation might be able to support the setting up of communities of practice within the community as well.

4. Step-by-step implementation

Having introduced the nine components, we now turn to a step-by-step timeline with concrete activities for principals. These activities are outlined in the section below and represented in [Figure 4 \(Let's REAP! components set against primary activities\)](#).

Remember that you can use the icon at the top right of each page to jump back to the document overview.

4.1. Form a local/district group of principals and vice-principals

Your first step is to connect with other principals. Depending on your territory, this may or may not be facilitated by the government. However, you are fully empowered to make connections with other principals to form a community of practice. Your territory may well have a national WhatsApp group for principals already. You need to form a group of a total of 6-8 people, consisting of principals and vice-principals. Here are some guidelines:

- **The group should not be too small nor too large.** A group of about 6–8 people from across 3–4 schools is ideal.
- Each school should provide **two** people so that you can work as a team. This should involve the principal; ideally it would also involve the vice-principal, but depending on school structures in your territory, the second person could also be an existing in-service coordinator or similar.
- It is really important that the **same two people from your school attend** week after week. The group is not about representing your school, but it is about forming a community of practice that can work together. To get to know each other, the same two people should attend week after week.
- The meeting can take place **face-to-face or remotely**. If at all possible, occasional face-to-face meetings should take place. You also have to think about schools where the principals may not be well-connected to the internet or may not have digital skills. It is particularly important that those principals are included in some groups. You could also organise some hybrid meetings: For example, if a principal at schools A and B have good digital skills, but a principal at school C does not, the principal C could meet face-to-face with principal A to join a video call with B.

- Establish **message-based communication channels** for your programme via WhatsApp to support each other.
- This group should meet every other week (i.e., every two weeks) for one to two hours, to discuss the progress of **Let's REAP!**. Holding shorter meetings every other week is imperative (as you will see below). You should not replace these meetings with a full-day meeting at the start of term — unfortunately, a single longer meeting will not have the same effect.

Details for the activities are provided in Section 5.1 below. In [Figure 3](#) the principals meetings are marked with “A”; in [Figure 2](#) the principals CoP is marked with “CoP 2”.

4.2. Constitute a **Let's REAP!** implementation team in your school

As a principal, enlist teachers at your school to support you in the implementation of **Let's REAP!** and constitute an **Let's REAP!** team. You may already have a school management team; in that case, it is not necessary to constitute a separate **Let's REAP!** team: **It is important that the **Let's REAP!** team is the main management team for your school.**

The team should be assigned to implement, oversee, monitor, and, where necessary, intervene in the implementation of the relevant **Let's REAP!** components in your school. This team should meet on a weekly basis. In [Figure 3](#), the planning meetings are marked with “B” and the teacher group meetings are marked with “C”.

The **Let's REAP!** team should consist of

- the principal,
- the vice-principal,
- at least two teachers,
- guidance counsellor.

The number of teachers depends on the size/type of your school. For a small primary school, two teachers may well be sufficient. For a large school (say with ECD, middle school, secondary school) you may want three teachers. Ultimately, the number of teachers is determined by the person-power that you need to implement the nine components. In particular, this includes the implementation of

- Component 2. School management and communication;
- Component 4. Teacher support and collaboration;
- Component 5. Formative assessment;
- Component 6. Inclusion, SPED, wellbeing;
- Component 8. Engagement with parents and family;
- Component 9. Engagement with community and community organisations.

If you can find a parent or a member of the local community, they could also join the **Let's REAP!** team. As with the meetings for principals ([4.1. Form a local/district group of principals and vice-principals](#)), it is imperative that this group meets at least once a week.

Figure 3. Weekly activities undertaken by the two communities of practice (CoPs). The meeting cycle for principals is marked "A" (corresponding to label "CoP 2" in Figure 2), the Let's REAP! team meetings are marked "B" and the teacher meetings are marked "C" (corresponding to label "CoP 1" in Figure 2).

It is important that the **Let's REAP!** team is the main management team for your school.

4.3. Start implementing

To support the **Let's REAP!** Implementation, an [Implementation Planning Tool](#) is available. It is a flexible tool intended to allow planning of **Let's REAP!** components to be tailored to be specific to the context of the Member States implementing it. The [Implementation Planning Tool](#) should be used as follows:

- Each of the programme's nine components has its own tab within the Tool. Review each of the tabs (labelled Component 1 to Component 9) and prioritise the activities most relevant to you. To prioritise the activities, review the indicative timeline for the implementation of each activity and indicate the appropriate months for implementation.
- Once you have decided on the order and sequencing of the activities to be implemented, enter them into the blank tab entitled 'Your Gantt chart' by copying and pasting them. Adjust or amend the timelines as necessary by entering or deleting the letter 'x' under each relevant month.
- There are a number of planning tabs. For example, you will enter the dates for the principals meetings and teacher professional development meetings.
- Similarly, there are a number of evaluation tabs. For example, after each principals' meeting and each teacher professional development meeting, you will enter brief information about that meeting.

Use the implementation planning tool to plan implementation of the programme in your school.

4.4. Important considerations

Some key points should be noted when planning the implementation of **Let's REAP!**.

The Let's REAP! needs to be context-specific

The programme was not designed as a 'model' or 'blueprint', or a 'one-size-fits-all' intervention. Careful thought needs to be given to the balance of emphasis given to the programme's different components in each school and each territory. However, it is important to maintain the overall rhythm of the programme (such as weekly meetings).

The programme is also focused on improvement, not only recovery

Clearly, 'recovery' and 'remediation' is important. However, we need to recognise that even before the pandemic, there were deep inequities as well as dissatisfaction with learning outcomes in the Caribbean. The programme is ultimately an improvement programme. The first step in this improvement is to help mitigate the impact of the pandemic. However, this is only the first step. The programme provides a framework for recovery and improvement, to be executed over the years to come.

There are no 'selection criteria' for schools

Given that **Let's REAP!** ultimately focuses on improvement, we note that the programme is designed to be implemented in all schools, primary and secondary. Different schools in different areas will have been affected differently by the onset of the COVID-19 pandemic and other events in different ways. However, all schools can benefit from the programme.

Let's REAP! does not target specific grades

The programme is not just intended for specific grades (e.g., for primary grades or grades where students change schools) — **Let's REAP!** is there to support all students. In particular, **Let's REAP!** will ensure that all students achieve specific skills. For example, any primary student who does not have the required skills in literacy and numeracy needs to be able to access recovery needs. This means that evaluating *all* primary students and identifying those most in need of intervention is a vital part of both the planning and the monitoring aspects of the programme.

Management, monitoring, communication

Management oversight, monitoring and communication are critical to the success of **Let's REAP!** implementation, as well as evaluating the effectiveness of its impact. Component 2 specifically focuses on management. Alongside activities, the [Implementation Planning Tool](#) contains suggested monitoring tools as well as results-based monitoring and evaluation frameworks.

Make sure all teachers participate

It is extremely important that all teachers in your school participate. If a teacher does not participate, it means that the children and young people in their care will not benefit from **Let's REAP!** as much as they could be. You may not get all teachers to participate immediately, but do keep encouraging teachers who are not yet participating. To encourage participation in the teacher professional development, you should put the sessions on the timetable.

The unit of transformation is the school

There is a lot of evidence on school improvement. An important insight is that teaching and learning is not just dependent on good teachers. A large part of successful learning depends on the environment in school — how teachers engage with each other, what environment the principal creates, and so forth. We sometimes say that the 'unit of transformation is the school'. Therefore, creating the community of practice in your school, with your teachers, is extremely important. Moreover, it is important that all of the teachers can interact with each other. Ideally, you would only have one group for the teacher professional development meetings (up to perhaps 20 teachers). If you are in a large school (with more than about 20 teachers), you may need more than one group.

Form a single group of teachers rather than smaller groups: The unit of transformation is the school.

Groups should not be small; you may be tempted to arrange teachers by department and form several small groups (of 2–4 teachers). However, you will then lose the 'whole school effect'; therefore, form larger groups across different departments.

Figure 4. *Let's REAP! components set against primary activities. See 3. The nine components (above) and 5. Implementing selected components of Let's REAP! (below) for further details.*

Component	Activities for principals and vice-principals
1. Leadership and accountability	Engage in the community of practice of principals (meeting every two weeks).
2. School management and communication	Set up the Let's REAP! team at your school (meeting every week).
3. Regional and national partnerships	Although there are no specific actions for this component, principals provide updates on the progress of regional and national partnerships as it relates to the Let's REAP! .
4. Teacher support and collaboration	Initiate your school-based community of practice of teachers focussing on learning recovery, with weekly TPD meetings. Ensure that actions decided during TPD are executed.
5. Formative assessment	Monitor that, as an outcome of the CoP/TPD, diagnostic testing takes place, and students participate in tailored learning.
6. Inclusion, SPED, wellbeing	Monitor that, as an outcome of CoP/TPD, provision for inclusion, SPED students, and wellbeing at the school are improved.
7. Resources and curriculum	Facilitate the introduction of the new curriculum, encourage sourcing of high-quality resources and promote curriculum innovation
8. Engagement with parents and family	Monitor that, as an outcome of CoP/TPD, engagement with parents and family is improved.
9. Engagement with community and community organisations	Monitor that, as an outcome of CoP/TPD, engagement with the community and community organisations is improved.

5. Implementing Let's REAP! in your school

This section discusses the nine components of **Let's REAP!** and specific actions that arise in each component. The recommendations and guidance below should be read alongside the activities in the [Implementation Planning Tool](#).

The recommendations below are meant to guide the implementation in your school, but they are flexible enough to adapt to your particular context. We recommend that you use the implementation tool to prioritise your activities. The guide is written in a step-by-step format with sections detailing activities, necessary resources and personnel and a timeline for implementation. The guide also contains a monitoring framework to track every component of **Let's REAP!**. We recommend consistent monitoring to measure progress and outcome.

Each section below focuses on one of the components, providing a tabular overview. You should read these sections in conjunction with the sections in [Chapter 3. Overview of the nine components](#) and, where applicable, with the sections in [Chapter 4. Step-by-step implementation](#).

Remember that you can use the icon at the top right of each page to jump back to the document overview.

5.1. Leadership and accountability (C1L3)

Prior to reading this section, read the introduction to this component in Section [3.1. Leadership and accountability \(C1L3\)](#). For this component, also make sure you are familiar with Section [4.1 \(Form a local/district group of principals and vice-principals\)](#), as this covers most of the actions required here.

Actions for principals/vice-principals

As a principal, participate in the leadership programme with principals/vice-principals from other schools (with support from your ministry of education as applicable; see Section [4.1](#)). This will enable you to form a community of practice to facilitate peer support among principals (drawing on skills, resources and information), as well as provide emotional and mental-health support.

You will constitute a **Let's REAP!** implementation team (see [4.2. Constitute an **Let's REAP!** implementation team in your school](#) and [5.2. Management and communication](#)) in your school and to start implementing **Let's REAP!** in your school (see [4.3. Start implementing](#)).

Resources available to you

↑ [Implementation Planning Tool](#): A resource with information on the various components supporting your planning.

↑ [Leadership for Learning](#). A leadership development programme, based on the 'Leadership for Learning' approach.

Success criteria

Submitting the feedback forms on the meetings with the other principals to the relevant MoE department.

Begin the **Let's REAP!**

Outcomes for children and young people

In secondary schools, set up meetings with the student council to solicit their involvement in the **Let's REAP!**.

Better leadership means better learning environments and, therefore, better learning outcomes for children.

5.1.1. Details about this component

Leadership for Learning (LfL) is an established leadership framework, which has these five principles:

1. Focus on learning in all activities;
2. Creating the conditions for learning;
3. Dialogue about learning;
4. Shared leadership;
5. Shared accountability.

Principals should establish a leadership group, consisting of several principals and undertake the [Leadership for Learning](#) programme. We recommend that principals set aside an hour every two weeks to meet with their peers (cf. [Figure 3](#)) and undertake the programme.

Importantly, the programme does not only introduce Leadership for Learning, but it also provides an opportunity for principals to talk to each other about the progress of **Let's REAP!** implementation so that there is accountability and constant monitoring.

5.1.2. Summary of actions for principals in this component

No.	Activity	Description
C1L3a.1	Establish a Community of Practice (CoP) among principals.	Form a local/district group of principals and vice-principals; in those groups, undertake the LfL programme. You will have support from national coaches. Ensure that you monitor and evaluate your progress and submit results/ evidence to MoE.
C1L3a.2	Conduct monitoring and reporting on student learning	Set up structures to enable teachers to monitor and report student learning. To be effective, principals/VP/senior teachers can collaborate with teachers and other specialist staff to interpret data and design interventions. This will enable an assessment of whether or not learning is taking place. Ideally, use data from diagnostic assessment. Formative and summative assessments can also be used. Monitoring learning should be systematic.

For more information about these activities, including staff, resources, timing and related activities, please see our [↑Planning Tool](#).

5.1.3. Summary of actions for teachers in this component

No.	Activity	Description
C1L3b.1	Teacher leadership and accountability	Teachers take leadership in their teacher professional development and in the classroom. Teachers are accountable for their own learning, as well as the learning of their students.

For more information about these activities, including staff, resources, timing and related activities, please see our [↑Planning Tool](#).

5.1.4. Summary of actions for students in this component

No.	Activity	Description
C1L3c.1	Student leadership	In primary and secondary schools, selected students, e.g., from the student council (secondary) and student leaders (primary) are included on the Let's REAP! implementation team. Student leaders must ensure that various groups are represented in the Let's REAP! . For e.g. ask questions about how the Let's REAP! caters for students with special needs and disability

For more information about these activities, including staff, resources, timing and related activities, please see our [↑Planning Tool](#).

5.2. School management and communication (C2L3)

Prior to reading this section, read the introduction to this component in [Section 3.2. School management and communication \(C2L3\)](#).

Actions

Your responsibility as principal is to plan and maintain the recovery programme (discussed in this section); this includes high-level decisions about how to utilise the school space as well as managing distance learning activities. There are **three** primary tasks that need to be managed at the school level:

1. **Set up **Let's REAP!** team to initiate and maintain the recovery programme.**

Initiating and maintaining weekly sessions for school-based teacher development (further described in [5.4. Facilitate TPD; Figure 4](#)); this includes undertaking diagnostic testing (further described in [5.5. Diagnostic testing](#));

2. **Coordinate **Let's REAP!** data collection protocol**

Implement data collection protocol for diagnostic assessment and ensure that it informs teaching and learning.

Report data to MoE. Such data includes student participation in **Let's REAP!**, outcomes of diagnostic tests, and overall progress of **Let's REAP!** in their school (performance of **Let's REAP!** team, TPD programme, student referrals undertaken, etc). Report data on diagnostic tests to relevant MoE department

3. **Coordinate TPD**

Establish a school-based community of practice, and initiate differentiated instruction to enable teachers to lead learning improvement and inclusion. Through the CoP teachers can support each other, overall **Let's REAP!** and school improvement goals.

Resources available to you

↑ [Implementation Planning Tool](#): A resource with information on the various components supporting your planning.

Success criteria

1. Submit your recovery plan to the relevant MoE department for review.
2. Submit TPD Schedule and results of diagnostic tests
3. Submit plan for creating stronger rapport with parents and community partners.
4. Submit inclusion plan.

Outcomes for children and young people

1. Selected student leaders/representatives facilitate improved communication between management and students.
2. Communicate school performance to students and motivate them to participate in relevant **Let's REAP!** components.

The following figure shows the primary activities that need to be considered in school management. They are further expanded upon in the following sections.

5.2.1. Set up **Let's REAP!** team to initiate and maintain the recovery programme

The most important task for you is to plan, initiate and maintain the learning recovery programme. The steps for this were described in [Section 4 \(Step-by-step implementation\)](#) above. Another critical step in this is to set up the **Let's REAP!** management team in your school (cf. [Section 4.2. Constitute a Let's REAP! implementation team in your school](#)). Ideally, this team would be an existing team of teachers at the school — you do not need to establish a fully new team if you already have a team available that is working on related issues. It may well be the case that you have already established a COVID-19 mitigation team or that you have a team that focuses on pedagogical improvements in the school.

The team also needs to be mindful of how to manage the school space (including, for instance, ventilation as a means of COVID-19 prevention), as well as managing distance learning activities.

As discussed above, the **Let's REAP!** team should meet every week (see [Figure 3. Weekly activities undertaken by the two communities of practice.](#))

The second requirement in school management is initiating school-based teacher professional development. This is further described [in 5.4. Facilitate TPD; Figure 4: A, F](#)); this also includes preparing teachers for undertaking diagnostic testing (further described [in 3.5. Formative Assessment](#)).

5.2.2. Implement **Let's REAP!** data collection protocol

This process involves putting measures in place to collect data on diagnostic assessment. The data must be used to direct pre-teaching and re-teaching activities. Ensure that you keep the MoE informed by providing data on diagnostic tests, TPD, school performance and so on. Doing so will help promote accountability. Follow the COVID-19 school management guidelines, e.g., reporting the number of children participating in **Let's REAP!** as per [the Implementation Planning Tool](#).

5.2.3. Coordinate TPD

Collaborate with a school-based community of practice to implement and monitor TPD. After deciding on sessions, ensure that appropriate frameworks are in place to evaluate TPD. Report evaluations results to MoE.

5.2.3. Additional actions

Component 2 is broad and encompasses almost all aspects of the programme. There are additional points for consideration that are detailed in the following components. For example, in **Component 4**, your role as principal is to ensure that protocols are in place to facilitate inclusion, SPED and well-being of students. Also, follow the COVID-19 school management guidelines, e.g., reporting the number of children participating in **Let's REAP!** as per [the Implementation Planning Tool](#).

For **Component 5**, building relationships with parents as learning partners, the **Let's REAP!** management builds relations with parents and caregivers, enlisting them as learning partners. This is further described [in 5.8. Support for parents and caregivers.](#)

In **Component 6**, building relationships with the local community, the **Let's REAP!** management team should establish links with community organisations, enlisting them as learning partners. This is further described [in 5.9. Community organisations](#).

It is imperative that you set up a **Let's REAP! implementation team in your school.**

5.2.6. Summary of actions for principals in this component

No.	Activity	Description
C2L3a.1	Establish and manage Let's REAP! team, implement the Let's REAP! programme.	Establish and manage the Let's REAP! team (principal, vice-principal and 2–3 teachers). The team should meet on a weekly basis. Specifically for secondary schools, you should include a member from the student council. Implement the Let's REAP! at your school.
C2L3a.2	Coordinate teacher TPD	Initiating and maintaining weekly sessions for school-based teacher development (Component 4).
C2L3a.3	Coordinate data collection and planning for learning.	Principals collaborate with teachers, relevant specialists and lead data team to interpret data and plan for learning. Rethink approach to data collection and establish lead data team if one is not in place as yet. The lead data team should analyse and collate all data. This analysis involves putting the single child together with the parent and curriculum response. This means connecting in school and out of school experiences to inform analysis and an in-depth understanding of each student.

For more information about these activities, including staff, resources, timing and related activities, please see [our ↑Planning Tool](#).

5.2.7. Summary of actions for teachers in this component

No.	Activity	Description
C2L3b.1	Actively participate in Let's REAP! team	Selected teachers become part of the Let's REAP! team. Those teachers join weekly LRIP team meetings. During those meetings, the implementation of the Let's REAP! is discussed and planned.
C2L3b.2	Support principal in data collection	Teachers/staff with skills in data collection can support principals' efforts. Teachers who do not have skills in data collection could support by providing necessary data requested by the principal.
C2L3b.3	Implement measures for inclusion, SPED and wellbeing.	Ensure that measures for inclusion, SPED students, and wellbeing are implemented (Component 6)
C2L3b.4	Build relationships with parents, community organisations and government	Building relationships with parents as learning partners (further described in Component 8. Support for parents and caregivers). Building relationships with the local community and government (further described in Component 9. Community organisations)
C2L3b.5	Communication with student council on Let's REAP!	The principal/VP maintains active communication with the school student council about how the school is performing.

For more information about these activities, including staff, resources, timing and related activities, please see [our ↑Planning Tool](#).

5.2.8. Summary of actions for students in this component

No.	Activity	Description
C2L3c.1	Participate in communication	In secondary schools, selected students, e.g., from the school student council, can contribute to improving communication between school management and students. Student council members communicate to other students about the performance of the school, seeking to motivate students to contribute to other components (C4-C9 in particular).

For more information about these activities, including staff, resources, timing and related activities, please see [our ↑Planning Tool](#).

5.3. Regional and national partnerships (C3L3)

Prior to reading this section, read the introduction to this component in [Section 3.3. Regional and national partnerships \(C3L3\)](#).

No specific actions for principals and schools.

Partnerships with parents are discussed [in 5.8. Support for parents and caregivers](#) and partnerships with community partners is discussed [in 5.9. Community organisations](#).

As we have outlined in Section 1, **Let's REAP!** does not just concern the principals and school. There are also actions to be taken for intergovernmental organisations as well as ministries. At the national level, strategic partners play vital roles in equipping schools to close learning gaps. The implementation document guides auditing, evaluating and establishing new partners and retaining relevant partnerships. Similar to the recordkeeping required by principals and schools, ministries will keep records of partnerships that were established, monitoring relationships, contributions, and arising needs.

As a principal and as teachers, you should watch for new regional and national partnerships being established and see how they might support the **Let's REAP!** in your school. However, otherwise there are no specific actions for principals, teachers or schools in this section.

5.3.1. Summary of actions for principals in this component

No.	Activity	Description
C3L3a.1	Share information related to progress being made at regional and national levels with teachers	Inform staff, parents and PTA about cross-sectoral partnership. Information should include the nature of partner support and exactly how your school will utilise the support to implement the Let's REAP! and improve school in both the short and long term.

For more information about these activities, including staff, resources, timing and related activities, please see [our !\[\]\(bdbc1f85c5acda5f361b2dba755dcb9f_img.jpg\) Planning Tool](#).

5.3.2. Summary of actions for teachers in this component

No.	Activity	Description
C3L3b.1	Participate in Let's REAP! staff meetings	Participating in Let's REAP! -related staff meetings will enable teachers to understand the nature and importance of partnerships for Let's REAP! success and longevity.
C3L3b.2	Join or support Let's REAP! partnerships taskforce	Teachers can either join their school's (or district's) partnership task force or provide support in identifying potential partners for community organisations.

For more information about these activities, including staff, resources, timing and related activities, please see [our !\[\]\(2a4282dc455b24a8719bbd3b8683d6a8_img.jpg\)Planning Tool](#).

5.3.3. Summary of actions for students in this component

No.	Activity	Description
C3L3c.1	Communicate information about partnerships to student body.	Student councils communicate news about new cross-sectoral partnerships to all students.

For more information about these activities, including staff, resources, timing and related activities, please see [our !\[\]\(c4aaed3b5c356fb84b11eeae3fb16d4c_img.jpg\)Planning Tool](#).

5.4. Teacher support & collaboration (C4L3)

Prior to reading this section, read the introduction to this component in [Section 3.4. Teacher support and collaboration \(C4L3\)](#).

Actions

Your most significant undertaking to support teachers is to establish a **school-based Community of Practice (CoPs) of teachers**, dedicated to improving learning outcomes for children. Such CoPs offer mutual support, development of teaching evidence-based practices, utilisation of diagnostic tests. Such school-based CoPs are also known as teacher-group meetings or teacher learning circles. Because CoPs need a definite focus they are normally established through a school-based teacher professional development programme. More specifically, they are established through a school-based teacher professional development programme that focuses on student learning outcomes. Therefore, your action is to establish a school-based teacher professional development programme. In due course, this will establish the CoP.

Another important aspect of teacher support involves **implementing a differentiated** programme to promote a culture of inclusion and overall learning improvement amongst *all* students. This will ensure that the most vulnerable student groups are reached and academic gaps are lessened.

In particular, as a principal, you need to enable and empower your **Let's REAP!** team to lead TPD in the school. That means ensuring that

1. the **Let's REAP!** team have access to you for advice;
2. teachers are encouraged to attend the TPD, including making space in the timetable for TPD sessions;
3. all needed resources are in place;
4. the **Let's REAP!** team are supported to deliver the session face-to-face in the school, or to deliver the sessions remotely;
5. monitoring and evaluation of TPD is planned and data reported to relevant MoE department.

Resources available to you

1. TPD materials, including
 - a. [↑Implementation Guidance: Teacher Professional Development \[Facilitators Version\]](#)
 - b. [↑Implementation Guidance: Slide Deck for Teacher Professional Development](#)
2. TPD evaluation forms.

Success criteria

Submitting the feedback forms on the implementation of TPD.

Outcomes for children and young people

Selected students are trained to serve as peer tutors

Student leaders assist in the distribution and collection of psychosocial forms

Let's REAP! was designed with flexibility around the implementation of its components. However, support for teachers in the form of teacher professional development (TPD) sessions should be considered an activity central to the programme's success. Implementing TPD is time-intensive and requires both planning and enthusiasm. However, school-based practice-focussed TPD has important benefits:

- TPD can be very effective in improving learning outcomes;
- TPD offers opportunities for peer support.

As much as possible, the TPD should incorporate the range of suggestions below to ensure the success of the **Let's REAP!**.

5.4.1. Scope and sequence

Just like a curriculum, the TPD sessions have been carefully scoped and sequenced by specialists. It is extremely important that you follow the sessions as best as possible, particularly during the first year. Over time, your facilitators will gain the confidence to adapt and develop new sessions.

Evidence shows that there are certain ways of undertaking TPD (or 'teacher training') that have an impact on learning outcomes. However, evidence also shows that some forms of teacher training do not have an impact on learning outcomes. Therefore, for the time being, it is important that you closely follow the TPD programme.

One of the most important aspects of TPD is 'rhythm'. TPD should not be undertaken in a single block (such as during the week). Instead, TPD must be undertaken in small, regular blocks. [Figure 5](#) illustrates the sequence of weekly TPD sessions.

Figure 5. This figure is derived from Figure 3. The Let's REAP! team meetings are marked "B", and the teacher meetings are marked "C" (corresponding to label "CoP 1" in Figure 2).

5.4.2. Ensure facilitators are aware of the sessions' technological requirements

The TPD programme can take place face-to-face (in schools). It can also take place virtually, using the preferred video conferencing software. If the programme takes place virtually, it is vital to make the appropriate technology provisions.

Just like teachers preparing for blended learning for students, facilitators need to be aware of the technological requirements necessary to ensure the smooth and time-efficient flow of the sessions. This is particularly important when sharing external media such as videos and presentations and includes:

- Being aware of the settings for sharing video/audio during calls;
- Remembering to make closed captioning visible for those unable to hear audio; and
- Running through third-party media beforehand to be able to start from identified bookmarks.

Technology can be challenging to use; however, adequate preparation ahead of each session ensures that the maximum time can be dedicated to achieving the outcomes of each session and that participants remain engaged.

5.4.3. TPD must fit with teaching schedules

In some participating states, time is already allocated for regular TPD sessions (such as in-service training (INSET) days or abbreviated school days). Implementation of TPD activities should be scheduled to minimise interference with the already difficult task of teaching in the new normal of the blended learning environment. Keeping teachers onside and engaged with the content is essential to ensuring the effectiveness of TPD activities.

We note that weekly sessions form a central aspect of the programme's TPD component. The sessions should not be blocked, e.g., to take place on a single day. Teachers must have time to teach between sessions; therefore, shorter weekly sessions should be organised instead of INSET or PD days.

It is imperative that all teachers participate in weekly meetings.

5.4.4. Why should teachers agree to spend weekly time on TPD?

The 'deal' that we propose is that teachers only participate in the weekly sessions (and the activities required as part of those sessions). Rather than making many demands on teachers (including teacher training), we ask teachers to participate in the weekly sessions. This regulates the time that is needed from the teachers.

5.4.5. Diagnostic tests

Following on from the previous section — managing teachers' time — we note that the process of learning how to use diagnostic tests and applying them in the classroom is part of the TPD activity. This may sound strange, but thinking about it from the teachers' perspective makes sense: The introduction of the tests and administering the tests is a focus of the school-based CoP, i.e., the practices that are

done within the school, rather than a one-off event. Therefore, it must be part of the TPD process. Diagnostic testing is further considered in [Section 5.5. Formative assessment](#).

5.4.6. Learning improvement

Importantly, the TPD programme is also where the provision for learning recovery is made. Through TPD, teachers are introduced to diagnostic testing (previous sections); this determines the students that need support in specific areas. The TPD further covers how this support can be given.

5.4.7. Summary of actions for principals in this component

No.	Activity	Description
C4L3a.1	Establish school-based community of practice (CoP)	Principals must establish a school-based CoP to allow teachers to support each other in accomplishing Let's REAP! goals and whole school improvement. The school-based CoP should support each other in diagnostic assessment processes.
C4L3a.2	Implement differentiated instruction programme	Implement differentiated instruction programmes that will more readily cater to the learning needs of a wider range of students, particularly SPED.

For more information about these activities, including staff, resources, timing and related activities, please see [our ↑Planning Tool](#).

5.4.8. Summary of actions for teachers in this component

No.	Activity	Description
C4L3b.1	TPD facilitator selection and support	Two peer facilitators need to be selected in each school. These individuals should be enthusiastic and dedicated. They will implement the rollout of school-based TPD. Each school should ensure that their pair of facilitators is paired with another pair from a different school. School management needs to oversee the selection and pairing process.
C4L3b.2	TPD planning and timetabling	<p>Determine whether sessions are held weekly or fortnightly. We recommend starting with weekly sessions, with the option for moving to fortnightly sessions later on.</p> <p>Principals should report the selected session dates to the relevant district or national coordinators.</p> <p>Develop contingency plans e.g. for technical issues/equipment failure (such as distributing materials via phone or hard copy in advance, using mobile networks instead of wifi etc.)</p>
C4L3b.3	Facilitate access to TPD-related resources	Decisions regarding how the Let's REAP! materials will be supplied should be discussed. Districts should decide whether handbooks will be printed or soft copies will be made available to teachers and facilitators. Also, each district should ensure that schools have the necessary equipment that facilitators should use to deliver the content. A contingency plan should be in place for equipment failure.
C4L3b.4	TPD reporting and evaluation	Plan the monitoring and evaluation of teacher performance after TPD. This should include self-evaluation as well as a summative evaluation at school level. Teachers can develop portfolios with evidence of their growth.

		<p>Set up a web-based form, through which facilitators and teachers can report participation in - and outcomes of - the sessions.</p> <p>Submit data collected on TPD sessions and teacher performance to MOE MoE to feed results of analysis back to schools.</p>
C4L3b.5	TPD - Co-facilitation and delivery	Teachers to co-facilitate TPD sessions and attend sessions regularly.
C4L3b.6	TPD Evaluation and Monitoring / Portfolio	Teachers participate in TPD evaluation and monitoring by completing necessary forms. Teachers develop a portfolio of evidence to represent growth.

For more information about these activities, including staff, resources, timing and related activities, please see [our ↑Planning Tool](#).

5.4.9. Summary of actions for students in this component

No.	Activity	Description
C4L3c.1	Peer tutoring	Students engage in peer tutoring with guidance from their teachers. Student leaders can assist in the distribution and collection of student evaluation of the psychosocial programme.

For more information about these activities, including staff, resources, timing and related activities, please see [our ↑Planning Tool](#).

5.5. Formative assessment (C5L3)

Prior to reading this section, read the introduction to this component in [Section 3.5. Diagnostic testing and student learning plans \(C5L3\)](#).

Actions

The **Let's REAP!** team at your school needs to develop a schedule for administering formative and diagnostic tests. The plans for formative/diagnostic testing need to accommodate SPED students. You should also plan for test administration face-to-face and remotely. Importantly, diagnostic tests should coincide with specific learning outcomes.

You need to make sure that the TPD sessions covering formative/diagnostic testing are undertaken by teachers, and that the teachers consequently administer diagnostic tests according to the schedules set.

Following the administration of the formative tests, the tests need to be reviewed. Learning plans for individual students need to be constituted and executed to enable learning recovery. Where necessary, students need to be referred to specialists or social workers.

These elements are all integrated into the school-based TPD programme; it is therefore important that the TPD programme is undertaken within the school, to offer a coherent backbone.

Resources available to you

1. Examples for routines and approaches to formative assessment
2. Diagnostic tests samples
3. Tools to analyse tests

Success criteria

Results from diagnostic tests submitted to the government.

Student learning plans produced.

Students enrolled in learning recovery activities accordingly.

Outcomes for children and young people

Students engage in peer tutoring to assist teachers in addressing academic gaps.

Given the immense loss of learning resulting from unprecedented school closures during the COVID-19 pandemic, it is critical to know where students are in terms of learning outcomes to ensure that academic gaps are addressed. During meetings with teachers and stakeholders from the OECS territories, it became apparent that some students had not been reached with the blended learning efforts. This trend is no doubt similar to other parts of the region. Also, the current volcanic eruption in St Vincent and the Grenadines exacerbated an already fragile situation. As emphasised by the **Let's REAP!**, formative assessment and diagnostic testing will enable teachers to gauge how much students know so that necessary interventions can be put in place to promote learning improvement.

It is imperative that you set up a **Let's REAP! implementation team in your school.**

A range of teaching strategies is included in the TPD programme to equip teachers to teach more effectively. Sample tests have been included with the TPD programme, which will be available for teachers to modify and use should they wish to do so. Importantly, diagnostic tools provide resources and guidance to equip teachers to engage the most affected and most vulnerable students and their families.

5.5.1. Summary of actions for principals in this component

No.	Activity	Description
C5L3a.1	Diagnostic tests developed and administered	Meet with teachers, support staff and or specialists to discuss the kinds of tests that will be used for diagnostic assessment. Designate one or two staff members from each grade to issue diagnostic assessments for the grade. This will involve printing and distribution for face to face. For online, it involves ensuring that tests are appropriate, e.g. not too long and can be easily administered.
C5L3a.2	Implement Formative/Continuous Assessment	Ensure that formative assessment measures are developed and implemented by teachers. Formative assessment results should be integrated into learning outcomes and data collection and analysis. It should also be done continuously.
C5L3a.4	Support teachers in the development of relevant assessment and individualised learning plans	Provide the necessary support to ensure that teachers are developing relevant assessments and individualised learning plans to cater to a variety of learning needs, particularly SPED. Where necessary, ensure that teachers and parents collaborate in interpreting test results and designing learning interventions. Submit all test results to the relevant MoE departments.

For more information about these activities, including staff, resources, timing and related activities, please see [our ↑Planning Tool](#).

5.5.2. Summary of actions for teachers in this component

No.	Activity	Description
C5L3b.1	Planning and administering formative and diagnostic tests	Choose tests that will be used, when they will be used, how results will be graded/evaluated, and how results will be used to identify struggling students in particular. Plan frequency of test scheduling. Where necessary, update or adapt new diagnostic tests. For example, if tests will be delivered online, ensure that they are not lengthy. You may find that the ICAN and ASER tests are highly usable.
C5L3b.2	Incorporate test results into lesson plans and pre- and reteaching activities	<p>During TPD sessions and otherwise, teachers devise lesson activities and lesson plans, incorporating diagnostic analysis to address gaps and offer differentiation (e.g. through pre- and reteaching activities).</p> <p>Combine TPD session lessons on diagnostic tools with own insights from previous observations, and consider how to carry out these activities in both face-to-face and blended learning environments. Use MoE guidelines to plan formative assessment and analysis of results. Collaborate with principals to plan analysis of results and reporting.</p>
C5L3b.3	Building diagnostic tests for SPED	SPED teachers and teachers who teach SPED students need support. Diagnostic assessment must be developed or adapted to take account of the needs and learning styles of SPED students.
C5L3b.4	Provide guidance for peer tutors	Provide practice and printed guidance for students who will tutor their peers. Guidance sheet should also contain model answers and prompts to check for understanding, anticipated errors and how to correct them.
C5L3b.5	Submit test results	Verify that teachers are using the appropriate frameworks to analyse and submit results from

		diagnostic tests. Test results should be submitted to the relevant MoE departments.
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For more information about these activities, including staff, resources, timing and related activities, please see [our ↑Planning Tool](#).

5.5.3. Summary of actions for students in this component

No.	Activity	Description
C5L3c.1	Peer tutoring	Students engage in peer tutoring to assist teachers in addressing academic gaps.

For more information about these activities, including staff, resources, timing and related activities, please see [our ↑Planning Tool](#).

5.6. Inclusion, SPED, wellbeing (C6L3)

Prior to reading this section, read the introduction to this component in [Section 3.6. Inclusion, SPED, wellbeing \(C6L3\)](#).

Actions

There are three primary tasks that need to be managed at the school level:

1. **Inclusive learning environment.** Consult with teachers, specialists, parents and students to raise awareness regarding the needs of students with special needs and disabilities, the nature of SPED and useful strategies. This also involves working with regional and international organisations for guidance on best practices. For example, organisations such as UNICEF details protocols on students with disabilities. Also, sister islands such as the Cayman Islands provide exemplary guidance on SPED. A key aspect of this process is to cultivate a culture of understanding amongst all students and provide SPED students with a voice in decisions about them. Also, consider involving them in raising awareness on the nature of SPED. By taking these steps, you will help promote an **inclusive** environment at your school.

The inclusive learning environment takes into account students with multiple disabilities: Collaborate with the MoE and other specialists to access **tools for diagnosing students with multiple and mild disabilities**. Tools and resources should be low cost and easily facilitate differentiation. Consider partnering with other schools, e.g. private schools to gain insight on relevant resources and tools that are available. Working with students with multiple disabilities would require an **inclusive approach**, such as the inclusive communication model from UNICEF.

Tools for diagnosis: Collaborate with specialists, teachers and MoE SPED Department to seek and identify low-cost **diagnostic tools** which can be used in assessment in a blended learning context. Some examples are suggested in the implementation guide. The key is to use diagnostic tools that are based on research, such as the ICAN and ASER tests suggested in

the guide. The diagnostic tools should be responsive to a variety of SPED needs within the blended learning context.

2. Promote the **psychosocial wellbeing** of students and teachers. In meetings with teachers from OECS, many expressed the need for the recovery programme to address emotional, social and psychological aspects of the lives of individuals. Some islands across the region have included psychosocial care in their recovery programme; however, there is a need for more work to be done so that *all* islands include it in respective recovery initiatives.
3. **Manage and support referral system:** Follow up on referrals for suspected SPED students and collaborate with relevant specialists to ensure that students are tested appropriately for diagnosis.

Resources available to you

[↑Implementation Planning Tool](#): A resource with information on the various components supporting your planning.

4. [↑Implementation Planning: SPED Referral Flowchart](#)
5. [↑Implementation Planning: SPED Internal Referral Form](#)
6. [↑Implementation Planning: SPED Support Plan Template](#)

Success criteria

A range of SPED students are diagnosed and teaching consistently responds to their needs.

There is greater awareness concerning the nature of SPED and student need.

Teachers are using referral tools to refer students who present as having SPED.

Outcomes for children and young people

More capable students engage in peer tutoring to assist teachers in meeting the learning needs of SPED students. To do this, students should be adequately trained and equipped with necessary strategies to assist their peers.

There is a strong need for more SPED support, SEMH support as well as specialist teachers and educational psychologists/school counsellors. As this means employing more professions, this has significant budgetary implications. As we have outlined in Section 1, **Let's REAP!** does not just concern the principals and school.

Intergovernmental organisations and national governments will work on issues related to SPED/SEMH support

Students with disabilities have been disproportionately affected by the pandemic, and additional attention should be given to evaluating their needs and providing support to ensure their achievement of critical skills. Educational psychologists and counsellors are also key staff in identifying and addressing issues with students' psychosocial wellbeing. Where possible, counsellors should be involved in TPD training, and consideration should be given to the need for longer-term plans for hiring more counselling staff.

As a principal and teachers, you should look out for changes in the availability of school counsellors and SPED teachers. However, otherwise there are no specific actions for principals, teachers or schools in this section.

Another key aspect of catering for the learning needs of SPED students involves advocacy. This entails building awareness, accessing appropriate resources and working with parents, teachers and specialists to ensure that learning needs of students are understood and met, even if not fully.

Involve students in advocacy.

5.6.1. Summary of actions for principals in this component

No.	Activity	Description
C6L3a.1	Develop inclusive learning environment	Develop an inclusive learning environment that takes into account the academic needs of a variety of students, particularly the most vulnerable groups such as SPED students.
C6L3a.2	Coordinate Psycho-social wellbeing programmes for students and teachers	Principals should ensure that measures are in place to support the psychosocial wellbeing of students and teachers. This would involve collaborations with relevant specialists, MoH and MoE departments.
C6L3a.3	Manage referrals and support	Follow up on referrals of cases of students with suspected SPED needs, and facilitate connection with relevant specialists as needed.

For more information about these activities, including staff, resources, timing and related activities, please see [our ↑Planning Tool](#).

5.6.2. Summary of actions for teachers in this component

No.	Activity	Description
C6L3b.1	SPED student evaluation / planning	Develop co-planning and co-teaching schedules with support staff Establish time to plan and evaluate teaching, student performance and next steps
C6L3b.2	Supporting SPED students	Consider how peer relationships, tutoring and mentoring for SPED students can supplement the activity of specialist teachers.
C6L3b.3	SPED student evaluation	Evaluate the effectiveness of peer tutoring, parental engagement, assessment etc.
C6L3b.4	Participate in TPD sessions	Some of the TPD sessions focus on support for SPED students. In particular, those sessions would focus on differentiation (planning lessons and small group activities) the various learning needs of SPED students.
C6L3b.5	Keep records, use support plans and referrals	Contribute to record-keeping and implement support plans as necessary. Understand and use referral mechanisms where necessary.
C6L3b.6	Search for content online	Utilise open source content provided by the school or otherwise as necessary and integrate into lesson plans.
C6L3b.7	Administer diagnostic tests and deliver feedback	Administer diagnostic tests to assess children's learning progress. Provide regular feedback to students.
C6L3b.8	Guidance for peer tutors	Teachers and SPED specialists should provide training/guidance for selected peer tutors to work with SPED students. The guidance should include

		necessary strategies, prompts, anticipated errors and model answers.
C6L3b.9	Partnerships with SPED specialists and organisations	Establish and maintain strategic partnerships with specialist SPED schools in the district to enable resource sharing, as well as with advocacy and support organisations such as Disabled Peoples' International North America and the Caribbean.
C6L3b.10	Keep records of SPED students	Maintain a record of students with SPED needs progress through the education system, allowing teachers to hand over and ensure a proper level of support.
C6L3b.11	Plan evaluation	Ensure that appropriate frameworks are being used for planning and monitoring consistently.
C6L3b.12	Engaging parents of SPED students	Devise plan to engage all parents of SPED students and develop novel means to involve those who are reluctant to participate. Devise a training plan for parents that will equip them with necessary skills to support their children at home. In cases where parents are unable to support their children, plan for an alternative form of support.

For more information about these activities, including staff, resources, timing and related activities, please see [our ↑Planning Tool](#).

5.6.3. Summary of actions for students in this component

No.	Activity	Description
C6L3c.1	Peer Tutoring	Students engage in peer tutoring to assist teachers in meeting learning needs of SPED students. Ensure that students are adequately trained and equipped with necessary strategies to engage SPED students.

For more information about these activities, including staff, resources, timing and related activities, please see [our ↑Planning Tool](#).

5.7. Resources and curriculum (C7L3)

Prior to reading this section, read the introduction to this component in [Section 3.7. Resources and curriculum \(C7L3\)](#).

Actions

For this component, your role will be to facilitate the introduction of new curricula, part of which involves planning and allocation of resource budget, and possibly resource pooling where necessary.

Ensure that teachers carry out relevant research to obtain quality resources that will support teaching and learning in ways that reduce academic gaps and promote school improvement. Furthermore, resources should promote inclusion, particularly for SPED and students from low-income backgrounds.

Finally, encourage curriculum innovation among teachers to ensure that learning is always customised to students' needs. This approach and those mentioned above will drive learning improvement in both the long and short term.

Resources available to you

[↑Learning Recovery Programme — Implementation Planning Tool](#): A resource with information on the various components supporting your planning.

Success criteria

Resource allocation plan and budget is completed.

Teachers are constantly carrying out research to source high-quality materials.

Outcomes for children and young people

Older and more competent students can support learning by participating in peer tutoring.

As we have outlined in [Section 1](#), the Learning Recovery Programme does not just concern the principals and school. Intergovernmental organisations and national governments will work on issues related to learning resources and the curriculum.

Accessing resources online is important. However, knowing how to acquire high-quality OER is critical to equipping teachers in middle-income countries (such as those in parts of the Caribbean region). Teachers are to source and create content relevant to their classroom context and needs. In this way, it will save time and provide access to a range of high-quality content. Moreover, students may access OER at times, but teachers are encouraged to promote safeguarding practices for the well-being of their students as they navigate online learning.

As a principal and teachers, you should look out for new resources being made available to support academic recovery and ensure their use through appropriate TPD, see [Section 5.4. Facilitate TPD](#). Otherwise, there are no specific actions for principals, teachers or schools in this section.

5.7.1. Summary of actions for principals in this component

No.	Activity	Description
C7L3a.1	Facilitate the introduction of new curricula material	Develop resource budget and plan allocation of resources. Consider whether pooling/sharing resources with other schools may be an effective solution.
C7L3a.2	Source and use relevant learning resources	Ensure that teachers carry out research on relevant learning resources which will be used to support teaching and learning. This could be accomplished in collaboration with the school-based CoP. Explore what resources are available in the community.
C7L3a.3	Encourage curriculum innovation among teachers	Encourage teachers to be innovative in the use of curriculum resources. This will ensure that resources are adapted to suit the context and learning needs of students.

For more information about these activities, including staff, resources, timing and related activities, please see [our ↑Planning Tool](#).

5.7.2. Summary of actions for teachers in this component

No.	Activity	Description
C7L3b.1	Resource inventory and allocation	Compile a list of resources that you will need (including both online and offline resources)
C7L3b.2	Ensure safeguarding of students and student information	Where students access online learning environments, ensure that students are using safe logins. Make children aware of the risks of accessing content online.
C7L3a.3	Resource storage and access management	<p>Teachers need to support each other in the use of resources.</p> <p>Ensure that all teachers in the school have access to the content repository.</p> <p>Ensure that all teachers know how to appropriately use the platform to source content.</p>

For more information about these activities, including staff, resources, timing and related activities, please see [our ↑Planning Tool](#).

5.7.3. Summary of actions for students in this component

No.	Activity	Description
C7L3c.1	Providing support through peer tutoring	Older students should support their peers by helping them understand how to use OER resources to enhance their learning.

For more information about these activities, including staff, resources, timing and related activities, please see [our ↑Planning Tool](#).

5.8. Engagement with parents and families (C8L3)

Prior to reading this section, read the introduction to this component in [Section 3.8. Support for parents and families \(C8L3\)](#).

Actions

Strengthen parents' engagement with the learning of their children. You can draw on the materials provided. The materials will be reviewed in the TPD sessions, and selected teachers will implement strengthened relationships between parents and schools (e.g., through parent-teacher associations). You should also collaborate with school counsellors or SPED specialists to devise meetings with parents to evaluate training and psychosocial needs.

Another essential aspect of your role is to coordinate the provision of psychosocial support for parents. This is particularly crucial in the era of COVID-19 as the home has become an important partner in the education of children. Coping with the challenges of the COVID-19 pandemic and providing the extra support required in blended learning can be a daunting task. Therefore, promoting the wellbeing of parents will equip them to support learning more effectively. If there is a SPED team/SPED teacher/s at your school, they could possibly lead efforts in this regard.

Finally, involvement of the PTA is critical in parental engagement. Thus, it is important that you keep the PTA updated on the progress of the **Let's REAP!** so that they could provide feedback to parents. To make this task easier, liaise with a point person on the national and local PTA.

Resources available to you

1. Parent and caregiver support manual.
2. [Implementation Planning: Parental Support for the Academic Recovery Programme](#).

Success criteria

The communication between the school and the parents improves.
Parents have access to specialists who will support their psychosocial needs.

Outcomes for children and young people

Older students can serve as peer tutors and assist in training parents to understand content for younger siblings.

Supporting parents, families, and caregivers is critical to the success of the **Let's REAP!** implementation. Support requires several approaches to ensure that parents are equipped to assist their children at home effectively. It also includes checking in with parents to ascertain their psychosocial needs. Another critical aspect of this support is finding alternative ways to engage parents who are not offering full support to their child's education. This may involve finding out why they are not engaging.

5.8.1. Summary of actions for principals in this component

No.	Activity	Description
C8L3a.1	Coordinate the provision of psycho-social support for parents	Ensure that measures are in place to support the psychosocial well-being of parents. This can be accomplished by designating relevant staff to assess the psychosocial well-being of parents.
C8L3a.2	Strengthen and encourage dis-engaged parents to support student learning	Collaborate with relevant partners to devise creative/alternative means of motivating disengaged parents.
C8L3a.3	Strengthen links with PTA	Coordinate with local and national parent-teacher associations to ensure that parents understand their roles and perform them effectively.
C8L3a.4	Report on Let's REAP! to PTA	Provide regular updates on Let's REAP! progress to PTA. Updates should include honest evaluation of progress, next steps and needs.

For more information about these activities, including staff, resources, timing and related activities, please see [our ↑Planning Tool](#).

5.8.2. Summary of actions for teachers in this component

No.	Activity	Description
C8L3b.1	Engagement parents according to engagement strategy	Apply the protocol for parental support, stating exactly what is expected of them in supporting blended learning.
C8L3b.2	Inform parents about the availability of new resources for learning at home	Inform parents concerning the availability of new content. Once the content is ready to be disseminated, inform parents and caregivers about its availability and make it available to them.
C8L3b.3	Disseminate and collect questionnaires	Send questionnaires to students' parents and ensure that they complete them to identify parents particularly in need of support.
C8L3b.4	Submit questionnaire responses	Submit responses to the school administrator in the required format.
C8L3b.5	Support dissemination of resources to parents	Support the dissemination of ARP resources to parents once available.
C8L3b.6	Identify, support, and refer	Identify students and families in need of intervention, engaging them directly, or referring to counsellors and/or SPED specialists where possible
C8L3b.7	Support parental needs assessment	Ensure the dissemination of the questionnaire produced by the MoE to assess the needs of parents and caregivers. Once questionnaires are returned, submit them to the relevant MoE department for processing.

For more information about these activities, including staff, resources, timing and related activities, please see [our ↑Planning Tool](#).

5.8.3. Summary of actions for students in this component

No.	Activity	Description
C8L3c.1	Sibling tutors	Older students with younger siblings can serve as peer tutors to help younger ones at home. They could also assist with supporting/training their parents to support younger siblings at home.

For more information about these activities, including staff, resources, timing and related activities, please see [our Planning Tool](#).

5.9. Engagement with community and community organisations (C9L3)

Prior to reading this section, read the introduction to this component in [Section 3.9. Engagement with community and community organisations \(C9L3\)](#).

Actions

In this component, you will set up a community engagement team (if there is not one at your school) who will lead efforts in working with community groups. Together with your team, you will **establish and or revisit engagement** with community organisations and support vulnerable learners as they engage with community groups. To work effectively with community groups, ensure that you establish a database with details of past and current community organisations that you work with. After you have assessed the list of community organisations, generate a list of possible new community organisations that can support the **Let's REAP!**, including SPED students. Then schedule a meeting with community organisations to discuss **Let's REAP!** goals and how they can support. An important step is to monitor and evaluate the contributions of community groups. Use the guide to develop a monitoring and evaluation framework for working with community groups.

In addition, collaborate with necessary MoE departments and other relevant organisations to ensure that background checks are in place when community groups engage directly with learners.

Also, as you collaborate with community groups, use the opportunity to **mobilise support** for **Let's REAP!**

Resources available to you

1. [Caribbean **Let's REAP!**— Implementation Planning Tool](#) Component 6 provides guidance on community organisations
2. Database with a list of community organisations
3. Staff with good community relations

Success criteria

Through your engagement with the community, community organisations and parents (as part of the community), additional learning opportunities (formal and informal) become available to children and young people.

Updated database with new and active community partners who will support the **Let's REAP!**

Background checks are in place to safeguard children when they engage directly with community groups.

Community engagement team is established to lead efforts in engaging with the community.

Outcomes for children and young people

More opportunities for learning means more opportunities for catching up. Learning in the community may benefit the SEMH of children and enable them to catch up outside of school.

Students take on leadership roles in community groups and serve as liaisons between school and community groups.

Community organisations play critical roles in socialising the young. In addition, many students already receive some form of mentorship from participation in community groups and clubs. The **Let's REAP!** implementation tool provides guidance on recognising and effectively engaging, training, and monitoring collaborative work with community groups. A holistic approach that involves the Ministry of Education, schools and parents is recommended to effectively engage community groups where it is most needed in each school context.

The guide recognises that community groups are equipped with professionals who can assist in equipping students and their families to close academic gaps. In addition, community groups may be an essential resource for reaching parents who do not provide adequate support at home and who may not know how to help their children effectively.

5.9.1. Summary of actions for principals in this component

No.	Activity	Description
C9L3a.1	Establish community engagement teams to work with local organisations and provide support to vulnerable learners	<p>Set up a community engagement team of about 2-4 teachers responsible for identifying and approaching community group leaders and relevant organisations/individuals. Involve teachers and auxiliary staff by providing information about the importance of community engagement for the Let's REAP! and overall school improvement.</p> <p>The task force will be responsible for working with community groups on either the local or district level.</p> <p>Ensure that proper background checks are conducted when community groups engage with learners.</p>
C9L3a.2	Mobilise support for Let's REAP! from Community leaders	Organise meetings with community leaders and relevant organisations/individuals to explain the Let's REAP! scope and content. Emphasise the importance of the role they have to play. Discuss potential ways they can complement the programme. Formalise and record mutual commitments.

For more information about these activities, including staff, resources, timing and related activities, please see [our ↑Planning Tool](#).

5.9.2. Summary of actions for teachers in this component

No.	Activity	Description
C9L3b.1	Join / support community engagement team	Join the community engagement working group or provide support by providing information contacts the school can approach.
C9L3b.1	Participate in Let's REAP staff meetings	Participating in Let's -related staff meetings will enable teachers to understand the nature and importance of partnerships for Let's REAP success and longevity.
C9L3b.2	Join or support LRIP partnerships taskforce	Teachers can either join their school's (or district's) partnership task force or provide support in identifying potential partners for community organisations.
C9L3b.3	Collaborate with students who are in community groups	Teachers should engage secondary school students who are in community groups by appointing them as liaisons between the school and community groups.
C9L3a.3	Engage partners	Work collaboratively with identified leaders, organisations, and individuals to define the scope of their role in the Let's REAP! .
C9L3a.4	Evaluate training needs & implement training process.	Evaluate the training needs of participating groups. Establish and implement training schedule, protocol and monitoring protocols.
C9L3a.5	Identify potential partners and review existing partnerships.	Identify potential partners and collaborators (in this case, nearby schools, community and faith-based organisations, service providers) who may help the Let's REAP! . Feed this information back to relevant stakeholders, including the district education management officer, if necessary. Carry out audits on all existing partnerships to determine the state and viability of existing partnerships.

For more information about these activities, including staff, resources, timing and related activities, please see [our ↑Planning Tool](#).

5.9.3. Summary of actions for students in this component

No.	Activity	Description
C9L3c.1	Serve as liaison between the school and community groups	Students take leadership roles in community organisations or serve as liaisons between the school and community organisation by supporting teachers and principals with relevant information about community groups, and helping community groups understand how to support their school.

For more information about these activities, including staff, resources, timing and related activities, please see [our ↑Planning Tool](#).

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Acknowledgements

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